

BREAKING: Göbekli Tepe Starmap Skulls

The Asymmetric Awen $\backslash/$ Plasmaglyph carved into skulls at Göbekli Tepe, a ratio comparison with the “turkey foot” glyphs of Kentucky, Alligator and Eagle Mounds of Ohio.

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ABSTRACT

The author recognized in a video about the Gresky paper, “Modified human crania from Göbekli Tepe provide evidence for a new form of Neolithic skull cult,” the asymmetric Awen glyph, which is actually the LaGrangian arrangement of the solar system post Shamash breakdown (proposed cause of the Younger Dryas Event). The correlation, the author thought, could not be coincidental. This initial study was conducted to see if the % differences were within reason. Though with Kentucky it is up to 41.2%, it is much lower with Alligator Mound (3.2% or more), and Eagle Mound is best, 0.91%. The ratio adherence of the central pole length (A) to the difference between left and right vertices (D) is rather close between the proposed skullmap (skull 3) and Eagle Mound: 8.7 vs 8.62, using basic trig ratios to give a rough length to A. The author proposes in this paper the next steps to confirming these studies, using tighter surveys and calipers on physical specimens, as well as access to the rock art of Kentucky. Finally, he speculates upon the possible meaning of these skullmaps in their utility, as well as orientation issues as the Earth revolved around the “Yggdrasil” or “tree of life” - the EDIN - in the sky.

Key Words: skulls - grooves - awen - plasmaglyphs - Göbekli Tepe - Eagle - Alligator - Mound - earthwork - Shamash

SYNOPSIS

The asymmetry of the grooved feature in the skull (see Figure 1) in the Gresky et al. study is not surprising. Nor is it definitive. However, through comparisons with the author's previous work on asymmetric awen "turkey foot" glyphs, we can make some conjecture about the purposes of the skulls. Pointedly, that they are being used for star maps. In this case, the subject being the LaGrange arrangement post-Shamash¹, post-Younger Dryas breakdown. In this paper the A/D ratio and other ratios are used to create a probability equation for similarity for the four sites, or the Tepe region vs. Kithiki region. Please refer to the studies from

the author's "Megafauna Extinction" Part 2², pages 3-9 for direct measurements already done.³

Figure 1 - Starmap Skulls with marked grooves; particularly Plate C (skull 3), Frontal and lateral view; credit: Gresky et al.⁴

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https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354010454_Addendum_2_Megafauna_Extinction_Events_Update_to_the_Thun_derbolt_Extinction_Model_the_Surprising_truth_of_the_Younger_Dryas_Event_that_Changes_Everything

2 https://www.academia.edu/69494988/Plasmaglyphs_Part_2

3 Note that once the Bluegrass Army Depot base is open to the public, and the Broaddus Site is available, there is another large asymmetric awen to measure on the ground. To date, however, the author has made no inroads there. See "Great Pyramids of Kentucky," for the LiDAR measurements of the mound/earthwork.

4 <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/sciadv.1700564>

STUDY

The author previously set forth that A is the length of the center segment, and D is the difference between the left and right vertices upon A. The study of ratios of C and B is not covered in this initial paper.

Unfortunately, the Awen is on a curve. Therefore the author used trigonometry to make an initial estimate of the A/D ratio to see if there is congruence of a “potential starnap” on the skull with the Kithiki “turkey foot” glyphs, Eagle Mound, and nearby Alligator Mound.

Figure 2 - “Skullmap”, the author uses the cosine of the frontal segment lengths, in a mm ruler on image to guesstimate the lengths. Without a physical specimen, there is no precision possible, nor is it necessary to use the calipers this time to find relative %difference and statistical likelihood. Credit: author

$$A = \frac{2}{\cos(14.5\pi/180)} + \frac{12}{\cos(24.5\pi/180)} \sim 17.84, D \sim 2.07 \tag{1}$$

As can be seen, the A/D ratio is **~8.62**
 Previous studies by the author have the Alligator mound (2 different surveys) at 7.2 and 8.35, Eagle mound at **8.7**, and the average of several glyphs at 14.68, but one reliable ratio only 9.34, though it be the most far off of the group.

The author thinks that as the likely, prevailing evidence, is that the entire sign is the “tree of life” or “Yggdrasil”, and the LaGrangian Arrangement, in its prime, perhaps? Or perhaps not, as there are symmetrical glyphs in the same Kentucky location at multiple sites, including State Rock, as per Coy, et al.⁵

What cannot be told from this, however, is the ultimate truth of the bodies. It is supposed to be Jupiter, Saturn, Mercury, Venus, and Mars. But given the age, the author now prefers Jupiter, Saturn, Neptune, and perhaps Uranus in early arrival. The electric-plasma energy exchange must have been quite phenomenal during the Tepe and maybe into the Archaic Period. It is not clear if the failure of this arrangement to hold the “Three Body Problem” is the cause of the collapse of mankind, or was it a barrage of material related to the death of Shamash, or the arrival of planet Uranus, or the destruction of bodies (KINGU, TIAMAT) by Marduk/Jupiter.

⁵ “Rock Art of Kentucky,” Coy et al., 1997, p. 112

This is not possible to know from this data alone. The author calls on the archeologists to cease missing quintessential details as these asymmetries, and compare the skullmaps with the nearby glyphs, materials, and ornaments. If you do not look for things, you will not see them when you should.

The other key issue, here, will be to compare segments C and B.

The author will do a rough comparison, without the trigonometry applied, as we assume similar curvature left and right in the frontal and sagittal planes:

B ~ 7.8

C ~ 13

Therefore C/B ~ 1.66

In the Eagle Mound study which shows the most correspondence, the C/B = 145/93 ~ 1.56; however in another measurement it averaged only 1.015 depending on how vector C was drawn.

However, if these were the same basic drawing, but taken at various angles, or times of the year; or if the event lasted so long it was separated by only years or decades, then it is plausible to see these differences as trivial. The point being, without a more precise measurement of the specimen, compared with a detailed survey of the Eagle Mound site, the author wouldn't encourage dismissing the C/B ratio.

As for Alligator mound, C/B ~1.12 to 1.3, depending again on how you lay out the vertices. It should be remembered, if the earth was rotating around the broken star, and its "entrails" "hung in a tree" because the plasma was the tree, then the vectors of B and C would by necessity alter as you rotate around the central body. Therefore the "conjunction" as seen from the side with a ratio of A/D, with D being the difference between the vertex origins of C and B, would constitute the "cosmic pole". Perhaps this would be interpreted as a war like opposition, or as an arranged agreement of royal family members, for family rule, depending on where one stood in the rotation.

The best mapping presumably was done during the equinox based on the habits of natives worldwide. But perhaps at the solstice of that solar system arrangement, the awen "peace sign" disappeared and left only a cosmic pole.

The %difference of the Eagle Mound and Göbekli Tepe skullmap A/D is 0.91%, which is highly statistically significant. The %diff with Alligator Mound is, however, at best 3.2% and at worst 19.7%. Again on the ground surveying is recommended.

As regards vs. Kentucky glyphs, using averages from a very crude study (getting to the rock art is difficult because the sites are protected and also difficult to find/climb to) is 41.2%. However, in the case where the glyph most closely matches, and assuming the rest of the site is part of a progressive study of ancient astronomers overseeing a prolonged event, then the %diff is only 7.7%. Assuming rock art and photographs give a 20% error margin the ratio might be as low as 7.47, more than covering the range needed. In short that site needs to be re-measured with caliper specifications, if we are to assume the ancient astronomers in the Sheltowee tried as hard as the Allegewi astronomers of Ohio. As was previously demonstrated with the Jovian Octagons, the Allegewi definitely used trigonometry to get extremely precise alignment with measured satellite arrangements of Jupiter North Pole vortex storms (which are created with Birkeland Currents).

None of these helps with the dating of the site, and carbon dating is only so good. However, the author will support a Tepe Period aging for all the sites, with the understanding that the dirt mounds would need maintenance for erosion.

SPECULATIONS

The author would like to propose a speculation that the skullmap is part of a veneration of the Great Man, that is the “body” of the dead star - based on Chinese treatments of the Shang Di ‘character’ and the various forms of the Squatter Man holding up the 3 or 4 “maltese” cross glyphs (star-planets, ie: gas giants)^{6,7}. In this speculation the ancients would either sacrifice someone for the astronomer, or the astronomer would venerate the tribal elder/chief with a denotation of the divine right to rule, or the astronomers’ pupil might apply the map to the skull of the astronomer, depending upon cultural needs. Perhaps they feared the conjunction would end, God would die, and the world be thrown into chaos. Perhaps it was a “birthright” (deathrite?) for entering the “Netherworld.” Whatever the case may be, they were clearly careful to note the aforementioned asymmetry with some precision.

As for the other “incisions” or grooves they could vary in many meanings to specific constellations, stars, the entering Sol (as our system approached it), there is no way of knowing. However, it’d be slightly unreasonable to call this a language. Plasmaglyphics at this stage appear to be rote recordings of what is seen, and not necessarily the equivalent of later Hebrew or Rongorongo plasmaglyphics. Perhaps something more akin to the Liushitong, but less advanced? Certainly if dating indicates, these could be separated by thousands of years, 5,000 or more. It is not to be wondered at, there are African tribes today that do not use writing or letters in language. What works needs not changing, if the gods decree it.

The author would recommend the reader scour the archeological record for more glyphs and repeat these studies, particularly the A/D ratios, and look for correlations.

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